

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIO-EPOXY AND RECYCLABLE BIO-EPOXY WITH MOISTURE ABSORPTION STUDY FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIO-EPOXY AND RECYCLABLE BIO-EPOXY WITH MOISTURE ABSORPTION STUDY FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

Mechanical tests to perform on bio-epoxy

Experimental results

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIO-EPOXY AND RECYCLABLE BIO-EPOXY WITH MOISTURE ABSORPTION STUDY FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

Tensile tests

Designation: D638 – 14

Standard Test Method for
Tensile Properties of Plastics¹

Dimensions (see drawings)	Specimen Dimensions for Thickness, <i>T</i> , mm					
	7 (0.28) or under		Over 7 to 14 (0.28 to 0.55) incl		4 (0.16) or under	
	Type I	Type II	Type III	Type IV ^a	Type V ^{c,d}	Tolerances
<i>W</i> —Width of narrow section ^{f,f}	13 (0.50)	6 (0.25)	19 (0.75)	6 (0.25)	3.18 (0.125)	±0.5 (±0.02) ^{g,c}
<i>L</i> —Length of narrow section	57 (2.25)	57 (2.25)	57 (2.25)	33 (1.30)	9.53 (0.375)	±0.5 (±0.02) ^c
<i>WO</i> —Width overall, min ^g	19 (0.75)	19 (0.75)	29 (1.13)	19 (0.75)	...	+ 6.4 (+ 0.25)
<i>WO</i> —Width overall, min ^g	9.53 (0.375)	+ 3.18 (+ 0.125)
<i>LO</i> —Length overall, min ^h	165 (6.5)	183 (7.2)	246 (9.7)	115 (4.5)	63.5 (2.5)	no max (no max)
<i>G</i> —Gage length ⁱ	50 (2.00)	50 (2.00)	50 (2.00)	...	7.62 (0.300)	±0.25 (±0.010) ^c
<i>G</i> —Gage length ⁱ	25 (1.00)	...	±0.13 (±0.005)
<i>D</i> —Distance between grips	115 (4.5)	135 (5.3)	115 (4.5)	65 (2.5) ^j	25.4 (1.0)	±5 (±0.2)
<i>R</i> —Radius of fillet	76 (3.00)	76 (3.00)	76 (3.00)	14 (0.56)	12.7 (0.5)	±1 (±0.04) ^c
<i>RO</i> —Outer radius (Type IV)	25 (1.00)	...	±1 (±0.04)

Specimen Dimensions for Thickness, *T*, mm (in.)^a

CNC Process in GALAXI LAB

Tensile tests

No water

Water Condition

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Tensile tests

Tensile tests

Mechanical Properties of Neat Cured Epoxy System*		
Tensile strength	MPa	75 - 85
Tensile strain	%	5 - 7
E-modulus	MPa	2,700 - 3,000
Flexural strength	MPa	130 - 150
Flexural strain	%	6 - 8
E-modulus	MPa	2,800 - 3,200

* Curing condition: 80°C/ 25 minutes + 140°C/ 4 hrs.

Experimental results validate the data provided by Aditya Birla

Tensile tests

Table 4

Tested modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν and tensile strength σ_T for each specimen.

Material	Specimen No.	E , GPa	ν	σ_T , MPa
PR 520	T1	3.51	.36	80.2
	T2	3.47	.36	85.1
	Mean	3.49	.36	82.7
LT-5078	T1	3.05	.36	68.6
	T2	3.02	.36	68.6
	Mean	3.04	.36	68.6

RTM epoxy

[Yukun Li et al., 2022]

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Tensile tests

Compression tests

Designation: D695 - 15

Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Plastics¹

FIG. 2 Compression Tool

Compression tests

Compression tests

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No Water Condition

Water Condition

Comparison Young modulus tensile/compression

Comparison strength tensile/compression

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$$K_{Ic} = \left(\frac{P_Q}{BW^{3/2}} \right) f(x)$$

where ($0 < x < 1$):

$$f(x) = 6x^{1/2} \frac{[1.99 - x(1-x)(2.15 - 3.93x + 2.7x^2)]}{(1+2x)(1-x)^{3/2}}$$

$$x = a/W$$

a Three Point Bend Specimen (SENB)

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Table 5

Tested qualified critical load P_Q and fracture toughness K_{Ic}, G_{Ic} for each specimen.

Material	Specimen No.	P_Q , N	K_{Ic} , $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$	G_{Ic} , $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{mm}$
PR 520	B1	86.7	2.01	1.01
	B2	91.9	2.09	1.09
	Mean	-	2.05	1.05
LT-5078	B1	98.1	2.29	1.50
	B2	97.3	2.34	1.57
	Mean	-	2.32	1.54

RTM epoxy

[Yukun Li et al., 2022]

EPOLAM 2063

Figure 4.10: Hygrothermal aging effects in K_{Ic}

K_{Ic} decreases of 20% with the water absorption

[Gustavo Q.Q. Characterisation of fracture toughness of epoxy resin after hydrothermal aging, 2013]

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To validate the test, the following value

$$2.5 (K_Q/\sigma_y)^2 :$$

must be lower than:

- B
- W-a
- a

Using experimental value $2.5 (K_Q/\sigma_y)^2 = 32 \text{ mm}$

Value does not comply with the ASTM 5054 Standard and therefore the test is not a valid K_{Ic} test.

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No Water Condition

Water Condition

Bending ISO 178

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Flexural strain	%	6 - 8
E-modulus	MPa	2,800 - 3,200

* Curing condition: 80°C/ 25 minutes + 140°C/ 4 hrs.

Average Experimental flexural is lightly lower than data provided by Aditya Birla

*shear modulus will be determined by FEA

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No Water Condition

Water Condition

Thank you

- the Faculty of Engineer Academic year 2021, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand.
- Aditya Birla Chemicals (Thailand) (ABCTL) for support bio resin.